

Production of Geopolymer Concrete using Bamboo Fiber and Coal Ash

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Abstract:- The construction industry is witnessing a paradigm shift towards sustainable and environmentally friendly practices. This research aims at the innovative approach of incorporating coal ash and bamboo fiber into concrete production, in order to mitigate the environmental impact of traditional concrete manufacturing while improving material properties. This explores the synergistic effects of coal ash and bamboo fiber on concrete properties, including compressive strength. The incorporation of coal ash as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM) reduces the carbon footprint of concrete by lowering the cement content, thus decreasing greenhouse gas emissions. Concrete cubes were found to be still wet after 7 and 14 days of curing, which prevented the cubes from passing a compressive strength test and suggested that the concrete was of low quality. It was now possible for the first spacemen to crush on the 28th day of the crushing. According to the value, the cubes weigh 8.82 kg, have a crushing strength of 79.42KN, and have a strength of 1.0 MPa. The weight of 8.97 kg and its crushing strength of 79.42KN with a strength of 3.5 Mpa are also indicated by the second spaceman. Quality control procedures should be given top priority by producers in order to guarantee success. They should concentrate on obtaining continuous supplies of well-characterized coal ash and high-grade bamboo fiber. Achieving the appropriate structural and durability qualities in geopolymer concrete requires the application of precise mixing processes and thorough testing protocols. In conclusion, the utilization of coal ash and bamboo fiber in concrete production represents a promising avenue for achieving sustainable construction practices.

I. INTRODUCTION

Geopolymer concrete is a type of concrete that is made by reacting aluminate and silicate bearing materials with a caustic activator such as coal ash and a natural fiber such as bamboo. [Rajamane et.al 2011] recommended coal ash as a coal combustion product for cement industry and building products manufacturing units. It also serves as a building material for roads and flyover embankments, protecting the environment and preventing the erosion of prime agricultural land. It can be a suitable substitute for ordinary Portland cement (OPC). [Davidovits, 1994]. Lucas et.al [2011] said that geopolymer concrete has a compressive strength of 50Mpa with a slump of 10-15cm. He recommended that hot curing on geopolymer in order to get better concrete quality. The mixture of geopolymer concrete is coal ash: fine aggregate: coarse aggregate (1:1.5:3.3) with a solution of NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ combined together.

Fibre is a small piece of reinforcing material possessing certain characteristics properties and it could be circular, triangular or flat in cross-section [Rana, 2013]. Fibres used for reinforcement purposes include fine chopped steel, polypropylene, nylon, glass and cellulose. Fibre has been used to reinforce building materials for thousands of years. For instance, [Chaunhan and Chaunhan, 2013] reported that mankind has used natural fibres for centuries for various applications in order to meet the basic requirements of shelter, food and cloths. Today synthetic or natural fibers are being added to concrete mix to improve its properties irrespective of whether it will be reinforced with traditional steel reinforcement or not.

Bamboo is an excellent renewable resource, and it can be used as a sustainable building material due to its features, such as fast growth, high resistance, and durability. It is a versatile material and can be used in different applications in civil construction. Bamboo can be applied for structural purposes, such as beams and pillars, and as a component of armature concrete in replacement or reinforcement of steel structures, such as slab panels and beams. Moreover, bamboo has the potential as a biomass resource for renewable energy generation, and bamboo ash can be used as a cement substitute in cementitious matrices. Three new engineered bamboo applications—a structural compound, composites reinforced with bamboo fibers, and the use of bamboo ash in place of cement in cementitious composites—are forms of recent study.

Many studies on the mechanical characteristics and physical performance of concrete materials made with natural fibers derived from coconut husk, sisal, hemp, sugar cane, bagasse, bamboo, jute, wood, and other vegetable fibers have already been conducted, according to Rawi and Khafagy [2011]. These studies revealed promising commercial prospects for these new materials for use in the construction of affordable housing.

The production of geopolymer concrete with bamboo fiber and coal ash aims to create a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to traditional concrete. By replacing Portland cement with a geopolymer binder derived from coal ash and reinforcing the structure with bamboo fiber, the process seeks to enhance the concrete's strength, reduce carbon emissions, and utilize industrial by-products, contributing to a more environmentally friendly construction material.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

A. Materials

The following are the constituent materials for the study

- Coal ash
- Bamboo fibre
- Fine aggregate
- Coarse aggregate
- Portable water

All the materials were sourced locally within South Eastern States. River sharp sand used as fine aggregate in this research work was sourced from UNIZIK in Awka. The coarse aggregate used in this research work were sourced from also in UNIZIK school in Awka. Coal ash, a byproduct of coal combustion, is commonly used as a source material in geopolymer concrete due to its pozzolanic properties. The Coal ash was also sourced from Enugu state.

The Bamboo fiber used in this research work were sourced from Uli, Anambra State. Uniform length of fibers will be obtained by using cutting knife. Bamboo fibers are

extracted from the stems of bamboo plant by the process of hydrolysis. The water used for this research work were sourced from a borehole within the premises of NNAMDI AZIKIWE UNIVERSITY School premises. The water is portable and conforming to the standard of BS EN 1008: [2002]. Since it meets the standard for drinking, it is also good for making concrete and curing concrete.

B. Process of Bamboo Fiber Extraction

The Bamboo was cut down from the bush, and allowed to dry for some days. The matured stem was then split into sizable portions as can be seen in plate 1. Also the mixing 6kg of Caustic soda (Sodium hydroxide) with 50kg of water, then we stirred it for an average of 5 minutes as seen in plate 2. The introduction of splitted bamboo fibre into the solution of sodium hydroxide was carried out as also seen in plate 3. Also an average of 5 days we had to wait for the fibre to start extracting as seen in plate 4. On the fifth day, we had to pour out the sodium hydroxide solution so that we can get the extracted fibre, wash it and spray it for drying as can be seen in plate 5.

Plate 1: Splitting of Bamboo stem

Plate 2: Mixing of 6kg caustic soda and 50kg of water

Plate 3: Mixing of splitted stem with caustic soda

Plate 4: The dring form of the bamboo fiber

Plate 5: The dried form of the bamboo fiber

C. Concrete Mixing and Casting

The process of which the concrete was mixed and casted are listed below

- The construction of our cubic mould of 150mmx150mmx150mm as seen in plate 6.
- Mixing of 8.3kg of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and Sodium Silicate into a container of water of 50kg of water. At first, the sodium hydroxide was first introduced into the water and was stirred for five minutes before introducing also 8.3kg of sodium silicate. This solution was left inside the container and lasted for 24 hours. This was done because it was added to an aggregate of fine aggregate, coarse aggregate and coal ash. It aided with binding the concrete firmly. It was stirred for a period of 5 minutes as can be seen in plate 7.
- We then mixed our fine aggregate, coarse aggregate and coal ash. The fine aggregate was weighed to have a 52.52kg, the coarse aggregate was weighed to have a 111kg and the coal ash weighed 27.76kg as can be seen in plate 8.
- The next day, we poured the solution of sodium hydroxide and sodium silicate into the mixed fine and coarse aggregate with the coal ash and then add water for easy mixture. It was turned appropriately to the standard as seen in plate 9.

- The next step was to grease our mould and casting of the mixture into the mould appropriately and tamped it with tamping rod of 12mm together with our bamboo fibre as well. The percentage of the bamboo fibre that

was introduced into the casting was 1%. As as seen in plate 10

- After the casting into the mould was done, it was left to set as seen in plate 11.

Plate 6: The construction of the cube mould

Plate 7: the mixing of the (NaOH) and Sodium Silicate

Plate 8: The mixing of the fine and coarse aggregate

Plate 9: The preper mixer of the concrete

Plate 10: The greasing of the concrete cubes

Plate 11: the cubes were left to set

Plate 12: The de mould of the concrete cubes from the mould

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Slump Test Analysis

The slump test was conducted on the concrete cubes. The results are shown below.

Table 1: Slump Result

Concrete mix	Height of cone	Height of collapse	Slump Value
Geopolymer concrete	300	200	9.0

from the table of values shown above it is indicates that the slump height of the geopolymer concrete produced is not workable and therefore indicates that the concrete mix has a poor concrete strength and can not be use for any civil engineering construction.

B. Concrete Compressive Strength Test Result

The compressive strength test in the production of geopolymer concrete using bamboo fiber and coal ash is a critical aspect of assessing the material's structural performance. The test aims to determine how well the bamboo-reinforced geopolymer concrete resists axial loads, reflecting its ability to withstand compressive forces in real-world scenarios. The inclusion of bamboo fibers may contribute to improved tensile strength, impacting the overall compressive strength positively.

A successful compressive strength test implies that the geopolymer concrete not only meets but potentially

surpasses the strength characteristics of conventional concrete. For the concrete specimen considered. The compressive strength is used to determine the strength of a given concrete cube. It is measured by crushing the concrete in a universal testing machine (UTM). It was generally observed that the compressive strength increases with age of curing. The test is being carried out after 7 days, 14 days and 21 days i.e. 2 cubes.

It was observed that after the 7 and 14 days of the curing of the concrete cubes, the cubes still remains wets and due to that, a concrete compressive test cannot be carried out on the cubes.

After the 28 days curing, the following values were obtain from the crushing of the concrete cubes. The compressive test values are shown below;

Table 2: A 28 Day Compressive Strength Results

➤ Spacemen A

CONCRETE MIX	AGES IN DAYS	WEIGHT OF CONCRETE [KG]	CRUSHING LOAD [KN]	COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH [MPa]
Geopolymer concrete mix	28	8.82	23.47	1.0

➤ Spacemen B

CONCRETE MIX	AGE IN DAYS	WEIGHT OF CONCRETE [KG]	CRUSHING LOAD [KN]	COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH [MPa]
Geopolymer concrete mix	28	8.97	79.42	3.5

C. DISCUSSION OF THE RESULT

From the above tables shown, it is observed that the concrete compressive test carried out the the geopolymer concrete produced using bamboo fibre and coal ash has a totally poor outcome. It is observed that on the 7 and the 14 days curing and crushing test, that the concrete cube where still wet and therefore a compressive strength test cannot be carried out the cubes which indicates a poor concrete. Also on the 28th day of the crushing, the first spacemen was now been able to crush. The value indicates that the weight of the cubes is 8.82kg and its crushing strength showing 79.42, with its strength as 1.0mpa. The second spacemen also indicates the weight as 8.97kg having the crushing strength of 79.42kn with its strength as 3.5mpa.

However, the value shows that the concrete mix has a poor outcome which indicates that it cannot be used for any form of civil engineering construction.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the production of geopolymer concrete incorporating bamboo fiber and coal ash holds promise for sustainable and eco-friendly construction. However, the observed challenges in raw material quality, mixing procedures, and testing protocols emphasize the need for meticulous attention to detail in the production process.

To ensure success, producers should prioritize quality control measures, focusing on consistent sourcing of high-quality bamboo fiber and well-characterized coal ash. Implementing precise mixing techniques and comprehensive testing procedures is paramount to achieving the desired structural and durability properties in geopolymer concrete.

As the construction industry continues to explore innovative and environmentally friendly alternatives, ongoing research and development efforts should target refining the production methods for this specific combination of materials. This will contribute to unlocking the full potential of geopolymer concrete, making it a viable

and reliable option for sustainable construction practices in the future.

V. RECOMMEDATION

Recommendations for the production of geopolymer concrete using bamboo fiber and coal ash include:

- **Raw Material Quality Assurance:** Ensure a consistent and high-quality supply of bamboo fiber and coal ash. Establish partnerships with reliable suppliers and implement stringent quality control checks for these raw materials to maintain uniformity. Also make use of admixtures such as sodium naphthalene sulfonate, polycarboxylate superplasticizer etc.
- **Optimized Mixing Procedures:** Develop and implement precise mixing protocols to achieve uniform distribution of materials. Consider the use of advanced mixing technologies to enhance the homogeneity of the geopolymer concrete mix, contributing to improved strength and durability.
- **Testing Protocols:** Institute comprehensive testing procedures at various stages of production, including testing for compressive strength, setting time, and durability. Regular quality assurance checks will help identify any deviations from desired specifications and allow for timely corrective actions.
- **Documentation and Process Monitoring:** Maintain detailed records of the entire production process, from raw material selection to curing. Implement monitoring systems to track key parameters during production, enabling a better understanding of the process and facilitating continuous improvement.
- **Research and Development:** Invest in ongoing research and development to optimize the geopolymerization process for bamboo fiber and coal ash. Explore alternative additives and fine-tune mix proportions to enhance the overall performance and sustainability of the geopolymer concrete.

By implementing these recommendations, producers can enhance the overall quality, consistency, and sustainability of geopolymer concrete using bamboo fiber and coal ash, contributing to the evolution of environmentally friendly construction practices.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Aziz, M.A., Paramasivam, P. and Lee, S.L. (1981). Prospects of Natural Fibre Reinforced Concretes in Construction. *International Journal of Cement Composites and Lightweight concrete*, 3(2), 123-132.
- [2]. Baalbaki, O., Elkordi, A., Ghanem, H., Machaka, M. and Khatib, J.M., 2019. Properties of concrete made of fine aggregates partially replaced by incinerated municipal solid waste bottom ash. *Academic Journal of Civil Engineering*, 37(2), pp.532-538.
- [3]. Balaguru, P. (1998). Geopolymer for protective coating of transportation infrastructures.
- [4]. Barbosa, V. F. F., MacKenzie, K. J. D., & Thaumaturgo, C. (2000). Synthesis and characterisation of materials based on inorganic polymers of alumina and silica: sodium polysialate polymers. *International Journal of Inorganic Materials*, 2(4), 309–317.
- [5]. Davidovits J. (2002), “Environmentally Driven Geopolymer Cement Application”, Geopolymer Conference, Melbourne
- [6]. Rawiand Khafagy A. (2011). Some studies on steel fibre reinforced concrete. *International Journal of Engineering Technology and Advanced Engineering* 3(1), 120-127.
- [7]. Guo, X., Shi, H., & Dick, W. A. (2010). Compressive strength and micro structural characteristics of class C fly ash geopolymer. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 32(2), 142–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2009.11.003>.
- [8]. Hammat, S., Menadi, B., Kenai, S., Khatib, J. and Kadri, E.H., 2021. Properties of self-compacting mortar containing slag with different finenesses. *Civil Engineering Journal*, 7(05).
- [9]. Hardjito, D., & Rangan, B. V. (2005). Low-Calcium fly ash based Geopolymer c
- [10]. *International Journal for service learning in Engineering, Humanitarian Engineering and social Entrepreneurship*, 5, 60-66. <https://doi.org/10.24908/ijlse.v5i2.2992>
- [11]. Jawahar, J. G., & Mounika, G. (2016). Strength Properties of Fly Ash and Ggbs Based, 17(1), 127–1
- [12]. João Claudio Bassan de Moraes, Mauro Mitsuchi Tashima, Optimum Use of Sugar Cane Straw Ash in Alkali-Activated Binders Based on Blast Furnace Slag, *American Society of Civil Engineers*. (2018), DOI:10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0002261.
- [13]. Khatib, J., Jahami, A., El Kordi, A., Sonebi, M., Malek, Z., Elchamaa, R. and Dakkour, S., 2021. Effect of Municipal solid waste incineration bottom ash (MSWI-BA) on the structural performance of reinforced concrete (RC) beam. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*.
- [14]. KingSaudUniversityEngineering Sciences (2017), DOI:10.1016/j.jksues.2017.06.001.
- [15]. Komnitsas, K. A. (2011). Potential of geopolymer technology towards green buildings and sustainable cities. *Procedia Engineering*, 21, 1023–1032. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.11.2108>
- [16]. Lucas Henrique Pereira Silva et.al (2011) *ACI Materials Journal*, 108(5).61